

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF ABŪ BAKR AL-KĀSĀNĪ'S WORK "BADĀ'I' AL-ŞANĀ'I' FĪ TARTĪB SHARĀ'I'" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF JURISPRUDENCE

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ABSTRACT

The opinions expressed in the article are formulated in accordance with the requirements of the methodological principles and traditional methods of the Ḥanafī faith. Opinions on social welfare are observed on the basis of modern standards based on the book "Badā'i' al-şanā'i' fī tartīb sharā'i'" al- written by the jurist of Samarkand, Abū Bakr al-Kāsānī, and based on the jurisprudence rules and legal arguments introduced in Central Asia in general, in particular in our Republic.

Key words: Badā'i', Şanā'i', Kāsān, farḍ, wajib, sunnah, evidence, ijma', qiyās, asl, 'Uşul, furu', permissible, Islām, sharī'ah.

Approaching the most important jurisprudential sources and works in the Ḥanafī madhhab from the point of view of periodicity and historicity, firstly, the sequence of jurisprudents, secondly, the tradition of teachers and students, thirdly, the scope of their work, fourthly, in which period, what kind of jurisprudential problems were revealed, and fifthly, in finding solutions to social problems in Muslim jurisprudence. which new methods have been created, sixthly, the views of the jurists and the development of usulul fiqh, furu'ul fiqh sciences, and seventhly, the religious, economic and social importance of the views of the jurists, and it creates opportunities to remember well.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as a result of the work carried out in this regard, the boundaries of jurisprudence are beginning to be seen more clearly. However, there is still a lot of work to be done in this area.

The task of organizing the sources of Ḥanafī fiqh and systematically conveying them to the minds of the young generation is a complex and demanding issue, and the process of organizing these works from a single center is a factor that can improve the efficiency of the work being carried out. It is observed that the above-mentioned procedure is not given much importance in the literature published today. It is clear that the volume of research and development activities being carried out in Uzbekistan is very significant. However, it is necessary to speed up the work of detailing the results of

completed master's and doctoral studies, bringing monographs and books related to them to the attention of scientists and the general public of readers.

To what extent understanding the essence of Sharī'ah issues is based on simple and fluent, and most importantly, systematic presentation of knowledge about fiqh method and furu' concepts.

At the end of the 20th century, after the shackles and nets of the former Soviet system were removed, Muslim peoples began to recover their religious heritage. In the history of the peoples of Central Asia, a great scientific and spiritual loss occurred during the period of more than a century that was lost in between. It is necessary to strictly adhere to the order of periodicity of the presented source literature in filling the gaps that have appeared as a scientific and spiritual loss of the people today. It is important to consistently sort out the great heritage left by the jurists and scholars of Mavoraunnahr on the basis of the norms of a collective approach.

The first factor that led to the creation of Abū Bakr al-Kāsānī's work "Badā'i'" is the work "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā'" edited by his main teacher 'Alā' al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad ibn Abū Muḥammad Samarkandi.

"This book belongs to the pen of Imām 'Alā' al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad ibn Abū Muḥammad Samarkandi. He was born in 362 AH and died in 438 AH."¹

Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf expressed his opinion on this topic and explained his views as follows: "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb sharā'i'" (Sharī'ah). The owner of the book is 'Alā' al-Dīn Abū Bakr ibn Mas'ūd ibn Aḥmad Al-Kāsānī (died in 587 AH). That person's nickname was "Malikul Ulama". Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad ibn Abū Aḥmad studied mainly in Samarkand. He thoroughly studied all the books of his teacher, especially the book "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā'". The teacher, who loved his student, married his daughter Fāṭima. Fāṭima also memorized her father's "Gift" and surpassed many men in science. Later, she gave correct advice to her husband and corrected his scientific direction. The fatwa issued by her father would certainly have Fāṭima's signature. Then the groom's signature was added to them.

Researchers call "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb sharā'i'" a commentary on "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā'". "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā'" was a well-arranged book with an addition to "Mukhtasar Qudūrī."²

¹ Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf. Fiqh lessons (Lesson 14). Furu'ul fiqh books. From the book "Fiqh directions and books". Article. 03.01.2019. <https://islom.uz/dars-qism/9584>

² Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf. Fiqh lessons (Lesson 14). Furu'ul fiqh books. From the book "Fiqh directions and books". Article.03.01.2019. <https://islom.uz/dars-qism/9584>

Shaykh, may Allah have mercy on him, says the following about the book "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā" written by 'Alā' al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad ibn Abū Muḥammad Samarkandi, the main teacher of Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī: "This book is the original of Imām Al-Kāsānī's book Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb sharā'i'."³

Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf, may God have mercy on him, did not comment on the Uzbek title of the book "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb sharā'i'" (Sharī'ah). (at this point, the honorable sheikh probably thinks that it is necessary to reflect on the translation of the title of the book, they did not give the Uzbek version). It seems that the question about the life of Allama Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī, that is, when he was born, remains open.

In the article "The role of Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī's works in pedagogy" by O.K. Chuboeva, "Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī grew up loving science and gatherings of scholars in his country. When he reached adulthood, he came to Bukhara and studied there under 'Alā' al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Abi Aḥmad Samarkandi (d. 539/1191)."⁴ (Note: 'Alā' al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Aḥmad ibn Abū Muḥammad Samarkandi⁵)

"The owner of the book is 'Alā' al-Dīn Abū Bakr ibn Mas'ūd ibn Aḥmad Al-Kāsānī (died in 587 AH)."⁶

Undoubtedly, there are inaccuracies in these available data.

But if we look carefully at "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb sharā'i'", we will see that it is not like the commentaries that have become tradition. It does not follow the method of interpreting the text of the original word for word. In his book, Imām Al-Kāsānī did not follow the order of "Tuḥfat al-fuqahā" and rearranged the chapters and chapters.

At the beginning of his book, the author of "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i' fī tartīb sharā'i'" gave brief information about the merits of jurisprudence after praising him, and narrated a verse from Bukhārī, Tirmidhī, Ibn Mājah and other muḥaddiths from Ibn 'Abbās, may God bless him and grant him peace: it is not prayed with something like being. A jurist is more fierce against Satan than a thousand monuments.

Also, the author notes that his predecessors had finished many books, but did not pay much attention to the order, and he wants to try to fill this deficiency

³ Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf. Fiqh lessons (Lesson 14). Furu'ul fiqh books. From the book "Fiqh directions and books". Article.. 03.01.2019. <https://islom.uz/dars-qism/9584>

⁴ Чубоева О.К. Абу Бакр Косоний и роль его трудов в педагогике. Ученый XXI века • 2020 • № 1 (60). file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/abu-bakr-kosoniy-i-rol-ego-trudov-v-pedagogike%20(1).pdf.

⁵ Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf. Fiqh lessons (Lesson 14). Furu'ul fiqh books. From the book "Fiqh directions and books". Article.03.01.2019. <https://islom.uz/dars-qism/9584>

⁶ In that place.

in his book. Then he begins to explain fiqh issues starting from “Kitab at-taharat.”⁷

One of the aims of this scientific work dedicated to the legacy of Allama Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī, including his book entitled "Badā'ī' al-ṣanā'ī' fī tartīb sharā'ī'" ("Artistic skill in regulating the laws of the Sharī'ah"), was among the scholars of his time. It is to show once again that the work was done in order to eliminate the complex difficulties that have arisen.

The difficulties that existed during the time when Allama Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī lived have come to the present time and are re-emerging as an obstacle in the face of modern science. In this respect, it can be seen that Imām Al-Kāsānī's great service to science was clearly demonstrated.

Muslim scholars and prominent orientalist scholars of the West also recognize that Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī's book "Badā'ī' al-ṣanā'ī' fī tartīb sharā'ī'" is of great importance in order to regulate the jurisprudence of Shariat. "Usually, books of furu'ul fiqh consist of three parts: prayer, treatment, family and other things, and crime.

Sharī'ah rulings on the issues of ablution, prayer, zakat, fasting and pilgrimage are studied in prayers.

Issues such as trade, various financial relationships, inheritance, wills, endowments, and issues related to slaves are studied in the transaction. The family regulation is also part of the transaction, in which attention is paid to issues such as marriage, divorce, idda, hazana, and pension.

Crimes include drunkenness, adultery, murder, bodily harm, and similar crimes, and their Sharī'ah punishments.

Of course, there will be separate chapters about personal life issues such as food, wine, halal-haram.

Also, rulings related to the external and internal relations of people, security, defense, captives, booty, etc. are studied in fiqh furu.

Furu' al-fiqh books are the most numerous books on fiqh. Even when the word "fiqh book" is mentioned in the mind of some people, books in this field appear. Books on the subject come in various sizes and shapes.”⁸

It is necessary to pay attention to the word "sharoi'" in the title of Al-Kāsānī's work " Badā'ī' ", which can be included in the series of books of Furu'ul

⁷ Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf. Fiqh lessons (Lesson 14). Furu'ul fiqh books. From the book "Fiqh directions and books". Article.03.01.2019 <https://islom.uz/dars-qism/9584>

⁸ Sheikh Muḥammad Ṣādiq Muḥammad Yūsuf. Fiqh lessons (Lesson 14). Furu'ul fiqh books. From the book "Fiqh directions and books". Article.03.01.2019 <https://islom.uz/dars-qism/9584>

fiqh, because the purpose of the author is at the heart of the words in the title of the work.

The definition and meaning of the word Sharoi' is given in the "Collection of Meanings" Arabic collection as follows: Sharā'ī' (noun), Sharā'ī' is the plural form of Sharī'ah."⁹

It is correct to say that Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī used this word in the title of his work to express the content of "laws of Sharia". In fact, the word "Sharia" is used in the singular form to express the meaning of "Muslim Sharī'ah ". The fact that Allama Al-Kāsānī used the word " Sharā'ī'" not in the sense of "laws" but in the sense of "rules of the law" comes from his views.

Dr. Muḥammad Fārūq Al-Nabahan (الدكتور محمد فروق النبهان) in his oral speech on the topic "Historical importance of Islamic jurisprudence" at the meeting of the Maghreb Academy held in Rabat on December 12, 2013, answered the question: "What is Muslim jurisprudence?" Muslim jurisprudence is a complex of detailed rulings derived from the common sources of Islamic Sharī'ah, and includes all statements made by all the scholars and scholars of all sects in the history of Islam."¹⁰

Dr. Muḥammad Fārūq An-Nabahan emphasizes that it is practical from a scientific point of view to study this process by dividing it into periods while highlighting the historical importance of Islamic jurisprudence. In this, the scientist emphasizes the following: "Legal scholars have proven that there are three major differences between Islamic law and Roman law. It is argued that these differences are reflected in its sources, characteristics, and general character of conformity, formality, and relationships between laws and moral norms. In 1949 AD, the International Conference on Comparative Jurisprudence held in The Hague recognized Islamic jurisprudence as the source of common law. This International Conference recognized the importance of Islamic jurisprudence as an independent and integrated jurisprudence and it serves as one of the sources of comparative jurisprudence.

In 1973-1974, the deans of law faculties recognized that the only way to harmonize Arab laws was to refer to a single source, Islamic jurisprudence.

The history of Islamic jurisprudence can be divided into five or six stages.

The first stage is the emergence stage. This is the period of Prophethood and is considered the stage of creation of Islamic jurisprudence.

⁹ <https://www.almaany.com/ar/dict/ar-ar/%D8%B4%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B9/>

¹⁰ Dr. Muḥammad Fārūq Al-Nabahan Historical significance of Islamic jurisprudence. 2014/01/26. <http://www.dr-mfalnbhan.com>

The second stage is the founding period (asri) in which the foundation of fiqh was strengthened, and this period consists of two parts.

1) The period of the first hundred years after the emigration of the Prophet and its characteristics.

2) the next 150 years and the period of the Imāms that took place in it.

The third stage is the period between 250-500 A.H., which is the stage of creation of major works and encyclopedias on Islamic jurisprudence.

During this period, such encyclopedic comprehensive jurisprudence collections were created as Imām Shāfi'ī's work "Al-Umm", Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī's "Badā'i' al-ṣanā'i'", and Sarakhsī's "Al-Mabsūṭ". "Al-Muwatta", "Al-Mudawwanāt", "al-Risālah", "Al-Kharaj" and six books of Al-Shaybānī can be included among such sources. Scholars have different opinions on the distribution of this period, and some believe that this phase lasted for three to four hundred years."¹¹

Regarding this topic, that is, the stages of development of legislation and Islamic jurisprudence, R.U. Malikov lists these stages in a slightly different interpretation. According to him, the stages of development of Muslim jurisprudence are as follows:

"The first stage is the lifetime of the Prophet (pbuh) and the period of the Companions (may Allah be pleased with them).

The second stage is the period of establishing the foundations of jurisprudence. This period starts from the 41st year of the Hijri calendar and lasts until the 132nd year.

The third stage is the period of establishment of jurisprudence and its use as a science. The period of sectarian imāms.

The fourth stage is the period of following and closing the gates of ijtihad. During this period, scholars conducted research within the framework of the four madhhabs that had been formed.

The fifth stage is the period of legal renaissance. This is the period after the gates of ijtihad were reopened and it was recognized that jurisprudence is valid for all conditions and all times until the doomsday, i.e. the current period."¹²

It can be said that Dr. Muḥammad Fārūq An-Nabahan took a more detailed approach in describing the stages of the development of Muslim jurisprudence.

¹¹ Dr. Muḥammad Fārūq Al-Nabahan Historical significance of Islamic jurisprudence.2014/01/26. <http://www.dr-mfalnbhan.com>

¹² Маликов Р.У. Введение в историю исламского права и его основы [текст]: учебное пособие / Р.У. Маликов – Уфа: Изд-во БГПУ, 2019. – 128 с. 11-61 <https://bspu.ru/files/75984>

The importance of mentioning these stages is that it helps to clarify the question of which period Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī is considered to belong to the class of scholars by jurisprudence scholars.

According to the opinions of a number of fiqh historians, Islamic law (fiqh) went through the following six periods in its development process:

First stage: Prophetic period;

The second stage: the period of the Companions;

Third stage: Tobiin period;

The fourth stage: the era of Mujtahids;

The fifth stage: the period of exiles;

The Sixth Stage: The Muqallids, i.e. imitators, or the age of imitation."¹³

Fiqh scholar Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī, like the jurists who can be included in the category of Tarjih jurists, carry out creative activities in the direction of translation between the words of the imām of his sect and the words of others, between the words spoken by the imām and the words spoken by the imām's students or other sects' imāms.

Among the Ḥanafī scholars of this class are Quduri and Burhān al-Dīn Marghinani, Allama Khalil from the Mālikī scholars, Imām Rafi'i and Imām Yaḥyā ibn Sharaf Nawawī Dimashqi from the Shāfi'ī scholars, Abul Hattab Mahfuz ibn Aḥmad Kaluzani Baghdadi from the Ḥanbalī scholars and the "Munaqhi of the Ḥanbalī Madhhab" (after reviewing Ḥanbalī jurisprudence, (who corrected some of his mistakes) include Qāḍī 'Alā' al-Dīn Mirvadi.

"The whole Islamic world reads the works of Qudūrī and Burhān al-Dīn Marghīnānī. In particular, "Al-Hidaya" is still taught as a textbook in world-renowned universities such as Al-Azhar. This authoritative book has been translated into English, Russian and other languages. The most important thing is that His Holiness Burhān al-Dīn Marghīnānī did not take any decision from the Qur'ān and ḥadīth on his own. Only the masters of the sect cited the rulings of the mujtahids. They are only able to say that some narrations are preferable to others, this is the most authentic narration, this is more clear, this is more in line with comparison, this is more useful for people. Such great people did not dare to take a direct judgment. They were among those who impartially served our religion to reach us in its pure state.

¹³ Zairiev A. The text of the lecture on the science of fundamentals of Islamic law. Department of World Politics. – Tashkent: 2013. – 126 p. – P.17. http://library.navoiy-uni.uz/files/islom_huquqi_asoslari.pdf

Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī, the author of "Badā'ī' al-ṣanā'ī'" can be recognized as one of the scholars of Ash'ab al-Tarjih period based on the classification of these periods.

In fact, it can be said that Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī's scientific activity and his work "Badā'ī'" made a great contribution not only to the development of religious knowledge, but also to the formation of the internal and external policies of Muslim state leaders. The primacy of Islamic jurisprudence in governing a Muslim society and state cannot be denied. The fact that scholars of jurisprudence had great influence and status in the Arab Caliphate is clearly seen in the example of Nūr ad-Dīn Maḥmūd Zengī 569/1174, Seljuk Sultan Mas'ūd I (d. 572/1176) and their descendants treating Abū Bakr Al-Kāsānī with great respect.

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